

EFFECT OF FINE MOTOR ACTIVITIES ON HANDWRITING PROFICIENCY OF PRIMARY FIVE PUPILS WITH DYSGRAPHIA IN KATSINA

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Abstract

The study examined the effect of fine motor activities on the handwriting proficiency of primary five pupils with dysgraphia in Katsina State, Nigeria. Two objectives and hypotheses were formulated for the research. The experimental research of the pre-test-post-test control group design was adopted for the study. The study population consisted of 110 primary five pupils from Charanci Primary School, identified as having dysgraphia, with a sample of thirty pupils selected for the study. They were selected based on the purposive sampling technique. Two instruments were used: Handwriting Proficiency Screening Questionnaire (HPQS) and Michael Handwriting Evaluation Scale (MHES), which were validated using the Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient, and the results showed that the tools were suitable for the conduct of the study, with the reliability indexes of 0.82 and 0.96, respectively. The experimental group received exposure to fine motor activities. The fine motor activities involved strengthening pupils' hand and arm muscles to help them (pupils with dysgraphia) feel comfortable writing and have more control over how the pencil moves. These activities include making shapes with matchstick, drawing small circles on a piece of paper, pouring water into small containers rubbing hands together, roll clay between fingers and tracing over dotted lines. T-test for independent samples tests the two hypotheses and analyses the effectiveness of the independent variables over the dependent variable. All the analyses were done, using SPSS (version 20) at 5% significant level. Findings show that the null hypothesis was rejected, meaning that Fine Motor activities significantly improved handwriting proficiency of primary five pupils. There was no significant difference in the handwriting performance between boys and girls in primary five. It is therefore recommended that fine motor activities be employed to improve the handwriting proficiency of pupils with dysgraphia.

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Introduction

Writing is a skill highly valued in society, even in an era of computers and technology. In the past, handwriting was prized because it was a primary form of communication; people sent notes to colleagues living in different communities. Now that typewriters and computers are used for communication between people, handwriting has become a rare form of expression. However, handwriting is still a critical skill of language and is needed for many reasons that people might not readily recognize. Writing notes, recipes, prescriptions, messages, checks, examinations, tests, taking minutes of the meeting and filling out applications are among a few reasons why development and teaching of handwriting skills needs to be continued in schools and at homes. Additionally, research has shown that handwriting is causally related to writing, and that explicit and supplemental instruction of handwriting are important elements in an elementary programme to prevent writing difficulties (Graham, Harris, & Fink, 2000).

Unfortunately, many students struggle in school because of dysgraphia, a problem of expressing thoughts in written form (Richards, 1999). Dysgraphia can have a negative impact on the success of a child in school; many children with dysgraphia do not keep up with written assignments, cannot put coherent thoughts together on paper, or write legibly. This disability needs to be recognized and remediated before it creates long-lasting negative consequences for the child. Pupils with writing problems have difficulties in writing to communicate their ideas; they may present difficulties in making sentences, using punctuations in sentences and using grammatically accepted vocabulary and paragraph organisation. It may be difficult for someone to read their handwriting, as some of them write letters upside down or mirror writing. Most of them have spelling mistakes in their writing. With these problems, they are always faced with poor academic achievement (Payne & Turner, 1999, & Strickland, Snow, Griffin, Burns, & McNamara, 2002). Another remedial treatment that has empirical evidence is building fine motor skills that build the muscles used for fine motor activities which can help improve hand functioning, which can lead to better handwriting (Berry, 1999).

Handwriting proficiency has been considered a prerequisite for later academic achievement. Handwriting proficiency is developed through practice writing. As young children draw scribbles on paper, they practice the eye-hand coordination and fine motor skills that are necessary for handwriting. These children should be provided with opportunities to practice their handwriting skills with a view to ensuring proficiency in handwriting. Handwriting is a foundation skill that needs to be developed early, as it affects students' reading, writing, language use, and critical thinking. Handwriting is taught at kindergarten at the same time as printing. Most students will achieve printing fluency by the end of second grade, and then fluency and speed with cursive handwriting by the end of fourth grade. In grade 5, children will develop their personal style that continues into middle and high school.

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When children are taught handwriting skills, they are able to focus on the content of what they are writing, rather than thinking about how to form their letters. When children acquire good handwriting skills, they write with speed and ease in all subjects (Marr, Cermak, Cohn, & Henderson, 2003; Feder & Majnemer, 2007). Greater writing speed will “lessen the burden on working memory,” enabling them to “create good reader-friendly prose” (Peverly 2006). Students who have mastered handwriting are better, creative writers (Graham & Harris 2005; Graham, Harris, & Fink 2000; Berninger 2012)

Dysgraphia is a disorder of writing ability at any stage, including problems with letter formation/legibility, letter spacing, spelling, fine and motor coordination, rate of writing, grammar, and composition. It may occur in isolation but is also co-exists with dyslexia as well as other learning disorders. Depending on the definitions adopted, at least 30% to 47% of children with handwriting problems also have reading problems (Hoorn, Maathuis, & Hadders-Algra, 2013). It can also be seen as a severe and extremely difficulties to write or express idea in writing; these may include activities such as filling forms, class work, homework, examination, and test, or even writing personal information to a friend. Difficulty in handwriting is categorized under many other neurodevelopmental disorders, such as attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder, cerebral palsy, and autism spectrum disorder. Research demonstrates that 90–98% of children with these disorders have handwriting problems. This is due to a lack of ability to integrate auditory, visual, motor and spatial skills require for writing, among other factors (Valenta, 2016).

Fine motor activities involve activities that hopefully strengthen hand and arm muscles of pupils with dysgraphia to help them feel comfortable while writing and have more control over how the pencil moved. Activities involved are: Making shapes with matchsticks. Drawing circles on a piece of paper, pouring water into small containers, rubbing hands together, molding clay, tracing over dotted lines, tearing paper and drawing circles on a piece of paper. The fine motor activities involved strengthening pupils’ hand and arm muscles to help them feel comfortable writing and have more control over how the pencil moves. Unfortunately, many pupils in primary school have handwriting problems, which affects their academic achievement. It is against this background that this study is based.

Objectives

This study investigates the effectiveness of fine motor activities as an intervention strategy on the handwriting proficiency of pupils with dysgraphia. Specifically, the objectives of the study were to:

1. determine whether or not fine motor activities affect handwriting proficiency of primary school pupils with dysgraphia,
2. find out whether there is gender difference in handwriting proficiency of primary school pupils with dysgraphia when exposed to fine motor activities,

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Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were postulated:

HO1 There is no significant difference in the mean score of handwriting proficiency between primary five pupils with dysgraphia exposed to fine motor activities and those that were not exposed to them.

HO2 There is no significant gender mean difference in the handwriting proficiency of primary five pupils with dysgraphia exposed to fine motor activities.

Methodology

Design

The experimental research of pre-test – post-test control group design was adopted. The pretest – post-test control group design requires at least two (2) groups, each of which is formed by random assignments. Both the groups were administered a pretest, the experimental group received treatment, while the control group did not. At the end, both groups were posttested (Gay, Mills & Airasian, 2009). Posttest scores were compared to determine the effectiveness of the treatment.

All primary five pupils in Charanci Primary School who were identified as having dysgraphia served as the population of the study.

The sample size of this study, twenty pupils with dysgraphia (boys and girls), were selected using the Handwriting Proficiency Screening Questionnaire (HPSQ); each of the two groups had ten (10) participants. The purposive non-probability sampling technique was employed.

Intervention Schedule

The intervention period for fine motor skill lasted for a half hour (that is, the length of the sessions), two days per week (Mondays and Tuesdays) for eight weeks. The weekly contact was between 9:30 and 10:00 Am. The experimental group received the exposure of fine motor activities.

The fine motor activities involved strengthening pupils' hand and arm muscles to help them feel comfortable writing and have more control over how the pencil moved. These activities include making shapes with matchsticks, drawing small circles on a piece of paper, pouring water into small containers, rubbing hands together, roll clay between fingers, and tracing over dotted lines.

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Two instruments were employed: Handwriting Proficiency Screening Questionnaire (HPQS), which was used to identify pupils with dysgraphia, while Michael Handwriting Evaluation Scale (MHES) was used to assess pupils' handwriting proficiency, with a reliability indexes of 0.82 and 0.96, respectively.

T-Test for independent sample was used to test the research hypotheses. All statistical analyses were performed using the SPSS version 20.

Hypothesis One

HO 1 –There is no significant difference in the mean difference of handwriting proficiency between primary five pupils with dysgraphia exposed to fine motor activities and those that were not.

Table 1: Summary table of T-Test of difference on Handwriting Proficiency between Experimental and Control Groups (N=20)

Variables	N	Mean	SD	df	t-cal	p-value	Sig.	Decision
Expr.	10	34.00	2.160					
				18	20.96	.000	0.05	H ₀ ¹ Rejected
Control	10	10.00	2.90					

The table shows the differences in the handwriting proficiency of pupils with dysgraphia in the Experimental (exposed to fine motor activities) Control Groups (offered no treatment). The T-test for independent sample was used to compare the two groups. The data of the experimental group show the mean of 34.00, SD of 2.160, while the control group shows the mean of 10.00, with SD of 2.90. The test showed t-cal value of **.000, p.005>.000..**

The null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference in the handwriting proficiency between primary five pupils with dysgraphia exposed to fine motor activities and those that were not is therefore rejected in favour of the alternate hypothesis, meaning that there is a significant difference in the handwriting proficiency between the experimental and the control groups.

Hypothesis Two

HO 2 There is no significant gender mean difference in the handwriting proficiency of primary five pupils with dysgraphia who were exposed to fine motor activities.

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Table 2: Summary Table of the T-Test between Boys and Girls on Handwriting Proficiency at Charanchi Primary School (N=10)

Variables	N	Mean	SD	df	t-cal	p-value	Sig	Decision
Boys	05	33.20	2.77					
				8	-1.190	.172	0.05	H ₀ ² Accepted
Girls	05	35.20	1.09					

Table 2 above shows the gender difference in the handwriting proficiency of primary five pupils with dysgraphia who received treatment using fine motor activities. The post-test data of boys show the mean of 33.20 with SD of 2.77, while the post-test data of girls show the mean of 35.20 with SD of 1.09. The t-cal value was **-1.190** at the probability value of .172. The result shows that there is no significant difference between the variables under study ($p > 0.05$). The null hypothesis, which says there is no significant gender difference in the handwriting proficiency of primary five pupils with dysgraphia, received treatment, using fine motor activities, is therefore accepted.

Discussions

The finding of the first hypothesis shows that there is a significant difference in the handwriting proficiency of the experimental and the Control groups. The finding that fine motor activities can be used in improving handwriting proficiency among pupils is supported by various studies. One such study was that reported by Texas Prekindergarten Guidelines (2018). The research found that 24 out of 32 kindergarten aged pupils who were involved in a daily specific fine motor programmes attained fine motor scores above the population mean for their age groups and significantly higher than the control group in the study (Brown, 2010). This is an indication that fine motor programs are beneficial to students in schools. This also supports the need for students and teachers to have the time, materials, and curriculum in order to develop these fundamental fine motor skills. A study carried out by Cameron et al. (2012) justified that using such test among pre-school aged children is topical because the result has shown that children's ability to use fine motor skills to copy designs was strongly associated with the gains in decoding, comprehension, and overall reading, once they entered kindergarten.

The finding of the study was also supported by a study of Copple and Bredekamp (2019);. By the end of the year, kindergarten students, who have had practice developing their hand muscles with activities such as writing, drawing, painting, working with clay, and constructing Legos, should have developed more fine motor skills .

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The finding on the second research hypothesis shows that there is no significant difference in the mean score of handwriting proficiency between the boys and girls of Primary Five with dysgraphia intervened with fine motor activities. This finding is supported by Mamman (2006), after a comparison of male and female dysgraphic (experimental) was performed at pre-and post-test. The result illustrates that there is no significant difference between the two groups. The position above was further supported by Case-Smith (1993); Exner (2005); and Pehoski, Henderson, and Tickle-Degnen (1997). They established that there was no significant difference between boys and girls on their performance on in-hand manipulation tests.

Conclusion

The findings of the research also concluded that fine motor activities were effective on improving handwriting proficiency among the primary five pupils with dysgraphia in Charanci Primary School because the experimental group demonstrated remarkable improvements after being exposed to the treatment. Therefore, the null hypothesis H_0^1 was rejected. The research findings further revealed that there is no significant difference between male and female pupils with dysgraphia exposed to fine motor activities in Charanci Primary School. This led to the acceptance of the null hypotheses (H_0^2).

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study and to improve handwriting proficiency among school children, the study recommends the following:

1. Fine motor activities should be used by teachers to teach handwriting skills to students with dysgraphia
2. Workshops for Special Education teachers and, by extension regular teachers of children, should be organized to educate them on how to manage children using several techniques of improving handwriting proficiency among the teeming number of pupils with dysgraphia in the mainstreamed classrooms of public schools, particularly using fine motor activities.

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